

Survey questionnaire: Internet use in libraries – policy, practice and pedagogy

NB – at the bottom of this page you can make a choice between seeing the survey adapted to computer screen format (standard) or to smartphone format.

Background

This survey is conducted as part of a national research project: *Internet use in libraries: policy, practice and pedagogy*.

The research project is commissioned and funded by the Heritage Preservation in Gothenburg, and conducted in cooperation with researchers Veronica Johansson and Maria Lindh from the Department for Library and Information Science, Borås University. The survey is conducted between December 2019 and January 2020.

This survey is one of several data collection methods in the project. The other methods complement the survey and comprise interviews and document studies of local library policies and rules (e.g. acceptable use policies, (AUPs), guidelines and user agreements for internet and Wi-Fi use), in a smaller sample of municipal libraries.

You can read more about the research project and the researchers at the project website at Borås University: <https://www.hb.se/en/research/research-portal/projects/internet-use-in-libraries---policy-practice-and-pedagogy/>

Purpose and target group

The purpose of this survey is to explore internet provision and regulation in Swedish public libraries today. We are interested in what differences in perceptions and approaches that may be found between different libraries, and what challenges and ways of dealing with these that can be identified.

The survey is directed to public libraries that are main libraries within their municipalities. This means that the survey goes out to 290 libraries that we have identified as the main library in each of the municipalities, by consulting the library database in Libris. It is to be answered by the library manager or other, by the library manager designated, suitable person with overview of the library's operations within the municipality and the questions raised in the survey.

In those rare occasions when the Libris register does not identify a main library for a municipality with several public libraries, we have chosen to send the survey to that public library that by name or other descriptor has been interpreted as "city library" or corresponding. We hope that the survey will be answered as intended by these libraries / library managers.

If, however, this survey invitation in an obvious way has been sent to the wrong library in a municipality (for example to a branch library or similar), we would greatly appreciate notification of this so that we can correct the mistake and send the survey to the intended library. If this should be the case, please contact us at e-mail address: internetpabibliotek@hb.se

If the survey instead has been sent to the wrong person or e-mail address, but within a correctly identified library, we hope that the recipient will help us by forwarding the invitation to the right person on their own.

Some library managers have already been, or are shortly to become, interviewed by us, as part of the complementary data collection in the project. We are very grateful for this participation in the study, but also ask, if possible, that you respond to this survey on behalf of your library nevertheless, so that we can get as high response rate as possible.

If needed, we encourage the respondent to enlist the help of others with special knowledge to answer questions in the survey.

Results of the study

The results of this survey will be published by the Heritage Preservation in Gothenburg as a freely available research report. The results will also be used for development of a pedagogic material with information and recommendations to public libraries concerning internet and Wi-Fi in the libraries' premises.

Participation and research ethics

This study follows the Swedish Research Council's ethical guidelines for social science research and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which means that:

- the survey is conducted anonymously in relation to us as researchers and to the Heritage Preservation through

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the use of the survey instrument Sunet Survey. This instrument ensures that there is no possibility for us to connect unique survey answers to a specific library, a person, an IP address, or similar by technical means

- unique libraries and staff in these will not be distinguishable in the following report or pedagogic material
- the answers to the survey will not be used for any other purposes than those connected to the research project as described above.

Remember however that in your capacity of civil servant in the Swedish context it is likely that upon answering this survey you will be bound by rules to handle the survey as a public document that is to be recorded in your public register. To simplify this process, if it applies to you and your workplace, you will be able download the survey and your answers as a pdf file upon completion of the survey.

If you have questions about this or anything else you are welcome to contact us researchers through the e-mail address: internetpabibliotek@hb.se

How to answer the survey

The survey consists of six parts. The first part contains a number of background questions concerning your library. The following five parts contain questions that are somehow related to internet and Wi-Fi (wireless network in the library's premises). The total number of questions in the survey will however vary between different respondents, depending on answers to different questions. The time required to respond to the survey can therefore also vary, but is estimated to about 10 – 25 minutes.

When you answer the questions it is possible to go back and check or change your answers to previous questions.

When you have answered all questions the survey is submitted by clicking the button "Send now". NB – if you wish to save or print your answers for the public document registry, you will now also have the opportunity to download the survey with your answers as a pdf file after you submit your answers (after you have clicked "Send now").

As the survey is conducted anonymously, it is not possible to pause your responses mid-way, close the window, and return at a later time. The survey has to be answered during one and the same browser session.

The survey is open until January 20, 2020, but swift responses are appreciated. Reminders will be sent out from time to time to non-responders.

Your participation is important

As the purpose is to produce a national overview and a solid basis for future recommendations and supporting material to the public libraries in related matters, we require a high response rate. We wish to thank you in advance for your help with this through your participation in the survey!

Sincerely,

Veronica Johansson, Ph.D., senior lecturer, the University of Borås

Maria Lindh, Ph.D., senior lecturer, the University of Borås

and

the Heritage Preservation in Gothenburg, Regionbibliotek Halland, and Biblioteksutveckling Sörmland

1. Which option describes your library best? (NB – all of the survey's questions about "the library" concern the "main library" of your municipality or corresponding exclusively – e.g. "city library". Information about potential branch libraries and similar are not to be included in your responses in this survey)

- Public library
- Integrated public and school library
- Other

If "Other", kindly specify:

2. How many active borrowers did your library have in 2018? (Use the numbers that you submitted to the Swedish National Library's annual statistical report)

- < or = 1000
- 1001 - 5000
- 5001 - 20000
- 20001 - 50000
- > 50000

3. How many employees does your library have? (NB: the question concerns number of individuals, regardless of their actual working hours and percentage of a full time position)

- 1 - 5
- 6 - 10
- 11 - 15
- > 15

4. If you add up the total working hours of your employees, how many full time positions (100 %) does that correspond to? Answer with a maximum of two decimal round off, e.g. 2,25.

5. Which county does your library belong to? (Only one answer possible)

6. Do you offer 'after hours service' (users may access the library's premises after hours when staff is not present) in your library?

- Yes
- No

7. Can the visitors use the library's public computers with internet access* during the after hours service? (* by "internet access" we mean access to internet searches, websites and services outside of the library catalogue). **[If Q 6=Yes]**

- Yes
- No

8. How many public computers with internet access* do you have in your library's premises? (choose the option that fits) (* by "internet access" we mean access to internet searches, websites and services outside of the library catalogue)

- 1-2
- 3-5
- 6-10
- 11-20
- < 20

12. Do you use filters on only some of your computers in order to limit the internet access for specific user groups? [If Q 9=Yes]

- Yes
- No
- Do not know

13. How have you defined the/those group(s) that you have chosen to limit internet access for? (describe in your own words) [If Q 12=Yes]

14. How do you control or ensure that the intended groups use "the right" computers (i.e. with or without filters)? Describe in your own words. [If Q 12=Yes]

15. Does your library use any other form of measure (besides potential internet content filter) in order to limit or control internet use on the public computers? Several answers possible.

- Yes, by open placement of computers so the staff can monitor use to a certain extent
- Yes, by checking computer logs retrospectively (search history, search terms) and follow-up with specific users if needed
- Yes, by requiring that users agree to certain terms of use for their internet access (e.g. to not visit certain sites / not seek out certain types of material)
- Yes, by providing information about what is not allowed in direct connection to the computers
- No
- Other

If "Other", kindly specify, and/or add additional voluntary comments to the question:

16. Does your library have a policy concerning use of Google Analytics on the library's website or other web based services that you offer to users / borrowers?

- Yes
- No
- Do not know

17. What are the main contents/purposes of this policy? Describe briefly in your own words. [If Q 16=Yes]

18. Do you inform your users somehow (directly or indirectly) that filters are used on some or all of the public computers? [If Q 12=Yes]

- Yes
 No

19. How and when do you inform the users about the filters? Several answers possible. [If Q 18= Yes]

- You have to have a library loan card in order to use the internet computers, and we inform about the filters in the terms and conditions for the loan card
- There is information about the filters on notes in direct connection to the computers
- Information about the filters appears on the computer screen in connection with user login
- Information about the filters appears on the computer screen if a search or search hit is blocked
- There is information about the filters in other places in the library's premises
- Other

If "Other", kindly specify:

20. Do the users of the public computers with internet access* have to identify themselves (with the consequence that their computer activities are traceable to their person)? (* by "internet access" we mean access to internet search, websites and services outside of the library's catalogue)

- Yes
 No

21. What ways of identifying themselves can the users choose between? Several answers possible. [If Q 20=Yes]

- Loan card number (with or without pin code)
- Social security number (with or without pin code)
- Login details for employees in the municipality
- Login details for elementary school pupils
- Other (describe what under "Comments" below)

If "Other", kindly specify:

22. Why have you chosen to keep internet use through the public internet access* computers anonymous? Describe in your own words (* by "internet access" we mean access to internet search, websites and services outside of the library's catalogue). [If Q 20=No]

23. Are the users required to sign or agree to a specific acceptable use policy (AUP) in order to use the internet (beyond library catalogue searches) on the public computers?

- Yes
- No

24. How is this signature or approval carried out? Describe briefly in your own words. [If Q 23=Yes]

25. Do you receive questions or objections from users of the public internet access computers with respect to the filters? [If Q 12=Yes]

- Yes, often
- Yes, sometimes
- Yes, but seldom
- No, never

If "Yes", kindly give examples of such user reactions (voluntary):

26. Do you think that the users of your public computers with internet access* receive enough information about the use of filters on these? (* by "internet access" we mean access to internet search, websites and services outside of the library's catalogue). [If Q 12=Yes]

- Yes
- No
- Do not know

Kindly motivate your answer:

27. Where/by whom was the decision to use filters on some or all of the library's public computers with internet access* taken? (* by "internet access" we mean access to internet search, websites and services outside of the library's catalogue). [If Q 12=Yes]

- The decision was made by the library itself
- The decision was made by the municipality or the municipal branch/division to which the library belongs
- The decision was jointly made between the library and the municipality / responsible division of the municipality
- Other

If "Other", kindly specify:

28. Has it been an active decision not to use filters on your public computers with internet access*, and if so - where / by whom has this decision been taken? (* by "internet access" we mean access to internet search, websites and services outside of the library catalogue). [If Q 12=No]

- Yes, it is an active decision that the library itself has made
- Yes, it is an active decision that the municipality has made
- Yes, it is an active decision made jointly by the library and the municipality
- No, it has not been an active decision
- Other
- Do not know

If "Other" or "Do not know", kindly specify/motivate your answer:

29. Has the decision to use filters on the public computers with internet access* caused any disagreement between library staff or between the library and the relevant external decision making authority? (* by "internet access" we mean access to internet search, websites and services beyond the library's catalogue). [If Q 12=Yes]

- Yes
- No

Kindly explain your answer (voluntary):

30. Has the decision to not use filters on the public computers with internet access* caused any disagreement between library staff or between the library and the relevant external decision making authority? (* by "internet access" we mean access to internet search, websites and services beyond the library's catalogue). [If Q 28=Yes]

- Yes
- No

Kindly explain your answer (voluntary):

31. Do you think that your library has enough knowledge and influence to be able to make decisions about filters on your public computers with internet access*, and to be able to take part in and influence such decisions? (* by "internet access" we mean access to internet search, websites and services outside of the library catalogue)

- Yes, definitely, and we lead or take active part in such decision processes
- Yes, but we have not been particularly active so far
- No, we lack the required knowledge
- No, we lack the required influence
- No, we lack both the required knowledge and influence
- Other

If "Other", kindly describe in your own words (voluntary):

32. Which of the following best describes the Wi-Fi situation (i.e. the wireless network) at your library? Multiple answers possible.

- The library offers Wi-Fi to its visitors and this Wi-Fi is entirely controlled by the library
- The library offers Wi-Fi to its visitors and this Wi-Fi is controlled by the municipality but unique to the library
- The library offers Wi-Fi to its visitors and this Wi-Fi is controlled by the municipality and shared with other municipal bodies (e.g. school(s), city council or similar)
- The library offers Wi-Fi to its visitors and this Wi-Fi is controlled by another actor (specify under "Other" below)
- We do not offer Wi-Fi to visitors in our premises

If "Other actor", kindly specify:

33. Who is responsible for selecting the supplier of this / these Wi-Fi(s) that you offer to the library's visitors? Several answers possible. [If Q 32=Yes]

- We / responsible person in the library
- Responsible person / division in the municipality
- Other
- Do not know

If "Other", kindly specify:

34. Who is responsible for the terms of use for this/these Wi-Fi(s)? Multiple answers possible. [If Q 32=Yes]

- We / responsible person in the library
- Responsible person / division in the municipality
- Other
- Do not know

If "Other", kindly specify:

35. Who, in the legal sense, is personal data controller (responsible) for the personal data (e.g. loan card number, user name and password, IP number, search history and/or similar) that are created when a visitor uses the library's / municipality's Wi-Fi on their personal unit (laptop, smartphone, tablet) in the library's premises? [If Q 32=Yes]

- We / responsible person in the library
- Responsible person / division in the municipality
- We have several Wi-Fi with different data controllers so it depends on which Wi-Fi the visitor chooses
- Other
- Do not know

If "Other", kindly specify:

36. Do you think it matters whether it is the library (on its own) or the municipality (as a whole / overall responsible) that is responsible for the Wi-Fi in the library's premises? [If Q 32=Yes]

- Yes, it matters
- No, it does not matter
- Do not know

Kindly motivate your answer (voluntary):

37. Do you think that the visitors that wish to use the library's / the municipality's Wi-Fi on their own units in the library's premises receive enough information about who is responsible for the service and the associated personal data management? [If Q 32=Yes]

- Yes
- No
- Do not know

Kindly motivate your answer (voluntary):

38. Are you aware of the increased library confidentiality requirements that came into force on January 1, 2018 in the Public access to information and secrecy act (OSL, 40 ch., 3 §), which now also states that: "Confidentiality applies in library operations concerning [...] information about an individual's use of information technology"?

- Yes, very aware
- Yes, somewhat aware
- No
- Do not know

39. To what extent have you in your library discussed what the Public access to information and secrecy act (OSL) means by "an individual's use of information technology"? (See question above)

1 = Not at all 2 = Very little 3=To some extent 4 = Quite a lot 5 = To a large extent

Rate your answer on a scale 1-5 where 1 = Not at all and 5 = To a great extent

40. If you have discussed the issue described above, have you arrived at a joint interpretation or application of what is to be included in the description "an individual's use of information technology" in the OSL Act, and that should therefore be protected with secrecy? [If Q 39=2, 3, 4, or 5]

- No, we have discussed the issue but not arrived at an interpretation
- Yes, we have discussed the issue and arrived at a joint interpretation

41. What have you decided to include in the interpretation of "an individual's use of information technology" as defined in the OSL Act? Several answers possible. [If Q 40=Yes]

- Information about who has used any of the library's public IT units (terminals, computers and similar)
- Information about what a user has been doing when using a certain public IT unit (e.g. search history, websites visited, cookie files)
- Personal identifiable information connected to agreements for using Wi-Fi in the library's premises
- Information about what a user has been doing when using a Wi-Fi connection in the library's premises (e.g. search history, websites visited, cookie files)
- Other

If "Other", kindly specify (voluntary):

42. In your opinion, does this new addition to the OSL Act lead to any problems or uncertainties for you as library and the visitors that wish to use the Wi-Fi offered in the library's premises? Describe in your own words.

- Yes
- No
- Do not know

Kindly motivate your answer (voluntary):

43. If an external person (e.g. journalist, private citizen) wants to take part of information about an individual's use of your public computers with internet access, do you think that you are able to safeguard secrecy to the extent that the OSL Act (see above) prescribes?

- Yes
- No
- Do not know

Kindly motivate your answer (voluntary):

44. If an external person (e.g. journalist, private citizen) wants to take part of information about an individual's use of the library's / municipality's Wi-Fi through private units in the library's premises, do you think that you can safeguard secrecy to the extent prescribed by the OSL Act (see above)? [If Q 32=Yes]

- Yes
- No
- Do not know

Kindly motivate your answer (voluntary):

45. To what extent do you think that the OSL Act, through the previously mentioned new addition, is formulated in a satisfactory way when it comes to the protection of individuals' privacy when using information technology in the library's premises?

1 = Not at all 2 = Very little 3=To some extent 4=Quite high degree 5 =Very high degree Do not know

State your answer on a scale 1-5 where 1= Not at all and 5= Very high extent

<input type="radio"/>					
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Kindly motivate your answer (voluntary):

46. Do you think that the library's authority / the municipality has enough knowledge about the public library's mission and conditions concerning the offering of free access to information and the protection of users' privacy?

- Yes
- No
- Do not know

Kindly motivate your answer (voluntary):

47. How do you rate your library's knowledge concerning possibilities and challenges connected to offering free access to information and the protection of individuals' privacy at this moment?

	1=Nonexistent	2=Limited	3=Medium	4 = Quite good	5 = Very good
State your answer on a scale 1-5 where 1=Nonexistent and 5=Very good	<input type="radio"/>				

Kindly motivate your answer (voluntary):

48. How do you rate the library users' / visitors' knowledge concerning potential threats to their integrity when using information technology in the library's premises (the library's public computers or their personal units through Wi-Fi in the premises) at this moment?

	1=Nonexistent	2=Limited	3=Medium	4 = Quite good	5 = Very good
State your answer on a scale 1-5 where 1=Nonexistent and 5=Very good	<input type="radio"/>				

Kindly motivate your answer (voluntary):

49. Is there anything that your library would need or wish for in terms of information, education, changed rules or similar, in order to improve the situation concerning the library's possibilities to protect individuals' privacy when using information technology in the library? Describe in your own words. (Voluntary question).

50. What social media do you use in any parts of your services that are directed towards users / borrowers? Several answers possible.

- Facebook
- Twitter
- Instagram
- WhatsApp
- Youtube
- Snapchat
- Messenger
- LinkedIn
- Other
- We do not use social media

If "Other", kindly specify:

51. What other digital platforms does your library use for services or other activities directed towards users / borrowers? (Multiple answers possible)

- Blog(s)
- App(s)
- We do not use other platforms
- Other

If "Other", kindly specify:

52. If your library uses apps directed to users / borrowers, specify which one(s) (provide a few examples). [If Q 51=App(s)]

53. Is your library subject to (bound to follow) any policy/policies concerning the use of third party services in connection with personal data management?

- Yes
- No
- Do not know

54. What is the main content / purpose of this policy / these policies? Briefly describe in your own words. [If Q 53=Yes]

55. What is your personal opinion about this policy concerning the issue of using third party services that collect and use personal identifiable information in the library's services / activities? Briefly describe in your own words. [If Q 53=Yes]

56. Finally: is there anything that you would like to add concerning the public libraries' opportunities and challenges in connection with free access to information, and the protection of individuals' privacy when using information technology (both through the library's own units and when users / visitors use the library's / the municipality's Wi-Fi for their personal units) in the library's premises? (Voluntary question).